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CONCEPTUALIZATION BY MATERIALIZATION DESIGN AND MATERIAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

With the rapidly emerging technologies of fabrication and manufacturing current impact of material upon form has become a prominent influence in architectural design. Fabrication promises to be not just a prototyping technique but a shift in the making of design. The current shift in design technologies requires a seamless design approach that supports the interdependence of form, structure and material. The paper presents a theoretical approach termed *The New Structuralism* (2010) and demonstrates a new relationship between the formal models of the architect and the materialization processes of the engineer. Furthermore, it presents a body of novel process models of design that changes modes of conceptualization in which form, structure and material are integrated in a single model of design.

Keywords: Conceptual Design, Materialization, Fabrication

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 EMERGENCE OF MATERIAL-BASED DESIGN

In craft, as in forms of vernacular building, material and the technologies of making are seminal factors in design (Sennett, 2008). In recent years the convergence of design and materialization technologies are promoting new material-based design practices in architecture, and other design fields. In design fields with a high material interface such as architecture and industrial design we are currently witnessing a transition in both theory and practice towards a level of involvement with material, and away from the primacy of form as a dominant model in design. Returning design to its material sources seems to contribute today to a new unified conceptual model. This important shift may be characterized as a holistic synthesis of conceptual

principles of spatial, structural and material ordering integrated within the logic of materialization and the rationale of fabrication and manufacturing technologies as a holistic model of design. This paper reports on a pilot research to define and characterize these developments and to identify their impact upon theories and models of design. The report attempts to formulate the theoretic foundations of tendencies in design under the influence of digital media and emerging material technologies. Through the collection and analysis of a body of case studies, first reported in the journal *Architectural Design* (AD) under the title, *The New Structuralism*, concepts and theoretical issues that are underlying these emerging design processes were identified. These emerging phenomena have broad implications for the ways in which we theorize, conceive, model, and undertake design. As such, the pilot research provides challenges to our conventional models of design, begins to identify new characteristics of digital design, and helps to formulate research issues into the paradigm of material-based design.

1.2 MATERIAL-BASED DESIGN: CONCEPTUALIZATION BY MATERIALIZATION

Over the last decade there have developed highly interactive processes of design collaboration between architects and structural engineers in *design engineering*. These approaches have developed new models and media for design that challenge orthodox methods of structural engineering. As a result a series of processes have evolved which define a new working relationship between the formal processes of conceptualization of the architect and the materializing processes of the engineer.

The traditional designation of the interaction between the architect and engineer has frequently

been one of post-rationalization. It has traditionally been characterized by the sequential development of *form*, *structure* and *material*. A formal concept is first conceived by the architect and subsequently structured and materialized in collaboration with the engineer.

No longer *a posteriori*, we have found that the design engineer is now involved at the earliest generative stage bringing to the fore the design content of materialization and fabrication technologies. It is characteristic of the cutting edge of contemporary design that technology mitigate between structural designs and the enhancement of the architectural concepts. Classic examples of collaborative design that accommodate material considerations early in the design process may be found in process descriptions of the Serpentine Pavilion, 2002 of Toyo Ito and Balmond with Toyo Ito (AGU, 2008) the collaboration of Ito and Mutsuro Sasaki on the Kakamigahara Crematorium (Sasaki, 2007, Kie et. al., 2004).

In much of this design, form, structure and material are integrated as having equal roles in design. Similar to vernacular architectural design, processes of design in both the conceptual and the materialization stages can be considered as a single continuous process.

Emerging fabrication and manufacturing technologies may be integrated in the design process from the early conceptual stages of design.

In the following section we present the background and the objectives of the pilot research. Following this introduction, the unique concepts and processes which we have characterized as material-based design are explicated. Finally, we consider the implications of these findings.

2. THE NEW STRUCTURALISM: PILOT RESEARCH

2.1 BACKGROUND

The primary goal of the pilot research was to select a case study sample of architectural and engineering collaborative design practices in order to investigate various design models in which form, structure and material play an integrated role from conception to fabrication/materialization design.

Through the analysis of the case studies, we have attempted to formulate the models of collaborative design and, particularly, how the structuring, encoding, and fabricating of material systems during the early design process have begun to contribute to the formation of a *material-based design* in which theories, digital methods and new technologies are contributing to novel models of design.

The main objectives of the pilot study were to select, explore and analyze case-studies, to provide a theoretical foundation for setting main research issues, to define the body of knowledge, models, concepts and principles and to present and illustrate their unique contribution to material-based design.

2.2 ACADEMIC FRAMEWORK- OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The pilot study was undertaken in the context of ongoing, long-term academic research in digital design in which *digital design* is seen as a distinctive and unique form of design thinking (Oxman, 2010). Making an attempt to understand how practitioners and designers think belongs to a long research tradition in design studies, (Cross, 2006). The following research attempts to continue this tradition.

The pilot study was undertaken over a period of eighteen months under the sponsorship of the British architectural and design journal, Architectural Design (AD). This international journal has had a long-term historical commitment to provide a professional forum for discourse in both theory and praxis. The research underlying this publication has put an emphasis upon the impact of engineering design and emerging technologies on the design process.

The original intention was to base the research upon a sample of fifteen of the leading practices in design engineering which had also been prominent in theoretical discourse and publication with respect to emerging technologies. The process of sample selection was undertaken through a literature survey in the fields of recent research and theoretical studies in design engineering and material technologies. The final selection included eight participants in design engineering and seven in material technologies. The latter group was diverse including architectural researchers in academic

contexts, experimental practices, new professional specializations, etc. Virtually all of the fifteen participants have some form of academic involvement.

The participants were either interviewed directly or by questionnaire. Eventually each produced a written document relating to the issues, concepts, practices and models which defined their experience of the relationships between architectural design, design engineering and material technologies. The publication of the book was followed by a workshop and symposium held at the Chair of Architecture and Digital Fabrication at the ETH Zürich.

With an important objective to define the emerging relationships between design, engineering and material technologies, the research methodology was based on a selection of a body of representative work comprehensive enough to foreground emerging theories, digital methods and computational technologies in design.

Among the main objectives were the following:

- Review and assess concepts and principles that demonstrate a unique approach with respect to joint models of material-based collaboration;
- Identify leading material-based design practices that demonstrate how materialization processes support novel models of design;
- Select case-study works that demonstrate concepts, principles and technologies which are relevant to the research issues of material-based collaboration;
- Demonstrate and document findings in the analysis of case-studies.

Cases studies were selected by the following criteria:

- Demonstration of a unique approach to collaboration in the conceptual stages;
- Development of a novel relationship between the formal models of the architect and the materializing processes of the engineer;
- Prominence in developing unique collaboration models which applied materialization processes during design conceptualization;

- Demonstration of synergetic *informing processes* in which form, structure and material can be integrated in design collaboration.

3. THE NEW STRUCTURALISM: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 THE NEW STRUCTURALISM

Today, there is now momentum for a revitalized involvement with, and return to, sources in material practice. The prioritizing of materialization is a dominant theme of the cultural shift which was termed: *The New Structuralism*.

The New Structuralism views the seminal importance of tectonic pattern as a cultural development turning away from formalism towards a material practice open to ecological potential.

The classical body of *The 'Old' Structuralism* is a body of theory and method devoted to defining *generic patterns* of relationships within a particular discipline that generate explicit instances within that discipline. The concept of structuralism is strongly associated with the work of the ethnographer Claude Lévi-Strauss. In his volume *The Elementary Structures of Kinship* he examined kinship systems from a structural point of view. Kinship was thus seen as a class of structural relationship between entities that shared a genealogical origin, through biological, cultural, or historical descent.

Structuralism has been applied in many scientific fields, including linguistics, anthropology, sociology, and psychology. In architecture, structuralism has emphasized the primacy of a rational and logical structure focusing on the investigation of configurationally structures.

The New Structuralism extends the principles of structuralism by re-interpreting the term *tectonics* as a basic concept that defines the structuring principles of integrated patterns (form structure and material). In relation to material-based design it is the affinity between tectonics and current digital and material technologies.

3.2 TECTONICS AND DESIGN

If, as has been proposed, generic patterns of spatial and material structures constitute important resources for thinking, doing and making designs (Mitchell, 1998), then the concept of tectonics

provides a seminal medium for explaining and managing the emerging relationships between conceptualization and materialization. That is, designers may conceive in terms of structural relationships and, in contemporary design, material fabrication structures may constitute a direct medium of conceptualization (Gramazio, and Kohler 2011).

Tectonics is a seminal concept that defines the nature of the relationship between architectural design and its structural and material properties. In different periods throughout history, tectonic discourse has continually redefined the elements of the tectonic relationship as well as their prioritizing. The origins of tectonic expression appear to reside in vernacular building traditions which achieve an integration of form, material, structure and construction. Vernacular architecture represents the essence of structural and material relationships in being a direct statement of constructional and material potential expressed structurally. The term tectonics was derived from the Greek word, *tekton*, meaning carpenter, or builder. The *tekton* later became the archi-tecton, and later, a master builder (Frampton, 1995). Gottfried Semper (1803-1879) referred to tectonics as a phenomenon that defined the use of different materials in architecture as a cultural phenomenon thus introducing an early cultural interpretation of tectonics. He was referring to an explicit reordering of the physical relationships of structure and material. According to Frampton, (Frampton, 1995) the ordering of architecture, structure, material and construction evolved from aesthetic and cultural interpretations of expressive qualities.

3.3 FROM TECTONICS TO INFORMED TECTONICS

The term *digital tectonics* was first introduced by William Mitchell (Mitchell, 1998). In contrast to Frampton, he postulated a virtual computational space that might accommodate the representation of materiality (thus creating a *virtual materiality*) and essentially supersedes the 'earthwork' that Gottfried Semper identified as one of the four elements of architecture. In the last decade since Mitchell's early thoughts on virtual tectonics, the theories and methods of digital design have contributed new

meaning to the term digital tectonics which profoundly advanced this concept.

New Structuralism relocates digital tectonics at the epicenter of a new materiality in design (Oxman, 2010). Performance-based digital models of design (Oxman, 2008) support material practice. Material performs by 'informed' explicit knowledge - the code of its making (Gramazio and Kohler, 2010). This change provides a reconciliation of the arguments of Mitchell, Frampton and Semper.

The changing definition of the relationship between form, structure and material may be considered one of the formative effects. *Digital Material* is now available for the designer as a new form of tectonic representation in which form, structure and material are informed in the processes of conceptualization. In order to accommodate the digital material in design, it was required to develop new forms of relevant knowledge and use informed processes for *digital tectonic design* and for *digital materiality*. The evolution of knowledge, concepts and methods is presented in the following sections as findings of the pilot research.

In a revolutionary way digital tectonics transforms the ontology of modernist tectonics from a logic of order and aesthetics to new structuring processes and behavioral models of form, structure, and material.

Furthermore this conceptual transformation from a static *a priori* relationship to a synthesis that is transforming the way in which we do design. Design now accommodates digital material in the early conceptual stages of design. In fact, in many respects, materiality is the basis for design conceptualization.

In order for this *New Materiality* to be possible, certain conditions of knowledge and methods have been evolved in theory and practice. Perhaps the most advanced level of the findings described below is in the form of knowledge actually incorporated within the tectonic - material model. For example, current software exists which optimizes the subdivision of geometric forms into optimal panel sizes for construction (Pottmann, 2010). In order to accommodate this level of synthesis, we propose the term, *Informed Tectonics*. This novel concept is motivated by shape, structural and material

properties integrated in digital rationalizing processes.

To conclude - it is the synthesis of the knowledge of architect, engineer and the fabricator within design systems that support informed processes of formation, structuring, fabrication and manufacturing. Informed tectonics may become a design media in of digital materiality.

4 MATERIALIZATION MODELS AND TECHNIQUES

Models and techniques that support information flow, that integrate the formal, structural and the materialization contents are currently recognized as a new area of research and rapidly evolving in design software design, in academic design research and in professional practice. Representative models tools are presented in the following sections.

4.1 ARCHITECTURAL GEOMETRY AS A RATIONALIZATION PROCESS

Deep knowledge of Architectural Computational Geometry (Pottmann et. al, 2007; Pottmann, 2010) has become essential knowledge in representing the integrated relationship between form, structure, material and fabrication. The theoretical foundations of architectural computational geometry share interdisciplinary knowledge in mathematics, computation, structural engineering and construction.

Digital tectonics encapsulates as foundational knowledge - the knowledge of Architectural Computational Geometry as the source of the profound reintegration of form, structure and material production. In order to support integrated processes and seamless workflow, geometrical modeling must also incorporate considerations of structural constraints, material properties and manufacturing technologies.

Figure 1. An example of construction-aware geometric design (Pottmann, 2010)

Rationalization processes for informed tectonics today constitute an active research area which aims at “providing construction-aware design tools and enabling a completely digital work flow from design conception to manufacturing” especially for highly complex geometries (Figure 1).

4.2 EVOLUTIONARY DESIGN

Tectonic systems which are composed of design components have certain design logic. This logic emerges from given structural and formal relationships of individual components in a bottom-up strategy (Bollinger, Grohmann and Tessmann, 2010). The evaluation criteria that characterize the logic of the system originate from the formal and structural relationships of the particular system. By running an optimization iterative process, best solutions of previous generation are selected. The individual components are reconfigured by mutation processes generating new iterations of satisfied solutions until architectural and structural criteria are satisfied (Figure 2).

Figure 2. *Diagram of the Evolutionary Algorithm: an initial population of random configurations gradually evolves until predefined properties are achieved.* (Bolinger, Grohmann, Tessmann, 2010)

This approach is illustrated by the LAVA's, VOxEL, extension for the Hochschule für Technik in Stuttgart, (Bollinger, Grohmann and Tessmann, 2009) The VOxEL project illustrates both the structural and the organizational principles in a conceptual model of square-edged sponge configuration. A finite-element-method analyzed the structural behavior was based on the logic of interconnected elements that presented a new typology. This logic can potentially be rationalized as a driver in fabrication processes which can be automatically derived from a 3d model.

4.3 FROM DESIGN TO PRODUCTION

The process of preparation for fabrication and construction may depend upon a reinterpretation of the tectonics of the project. Frequently this is done by re-use of the digital core model of the project as Scheurer (Scheurer, 2010) has described in his work on the digital production process for the formwork on the Mercedes-Benz Museum, Stuttgart by UN Studio and Werner Sobek.

Scheurer and Designtoproduction have pioneered processes of both construction and fabrication technologies (Figure 3).

Figure 3. 'designtoproduction' created a reference geometry of the roof and generated 3D-models of different types of timber components for Shigeru Ban - Nine Bridges Golf Resort Yeosu in South Korea (Scheurer, 2010)

The point here is that the data of the digital core (design) model can inform fabrication processes. Generated 3D-models of different types of timber components were generated by the reference geometry of the roof.

In a reversal of this process, it is possible that the performance can drive the design process of material systems, a condition which is highly significant in performance-based design.

5 DIGITAL MATERIALITY - AS A GENERATIVE MODEL AND TECHNIQUES

5.1 FABRICATION AS A GENERATIVE MODEL

Fabrication is not just a modeling technique, but a revolution in the generation and making of design. With the emerging technologies of fabrication the current impact of material and materialization concepts upon architectural form has become one of the prominent influences in contemporary design. A *priori* design by material is becoming a form in which the synthesis of architect, engineer and fabricator again controls the responsibility for the total processes of conceptualization and materialization. Computational programming of production data integrates design with the materialization process. Material conditions and assembly logic are now integrated and used as the basis for design generation. This re-defines fabrication as a generative process.

In the following sections we briefly introduce certain concepts models and techniques which relate to *digital tectonics*, *digital materiality* and *digital fabrication*.

5.2 DIGITAL MATERIALITY - THE ENCODING MODEL

Digital fabrication and the encoding of production data integrates design with the materialization process (Gramazio and Kohler, 2010; Bechtold, 2010). Digital fabrication, including robotic fabrication, can extend the scale of conventional construction methods and of current craft-based fabrication methods by enabling the performance of complex and large scale *customized* tasks. This process potentially shapes both the design of structural and material elements in an encoded formal design process. In this case, the construction process may be robotically controlled. This

customization potential also contributes to the function of fabrication as a generative process. Material-based design components such as bricks which have certain geometrical attributes and a constructional logic are encoded digitally according to their specific logic as a particular *material system* (Figure 4). Superimposed upon the material system logic is the encoding of desired macro-design geometrical properties. These are designed according to their unique assembly-logic that represents both shape and material in the desired organizational geometric pattern. Digital design code of complex (material) instructions can now drive design production, e.g. in robotic brick-laying. Furthermore, larger building scale elements can be designed as material systems that behave and adapt according to a specifically desired materials and assembly logic (Figure 4).

Figure 4 The Sequential Wall, Zurich, Switzerland, 2008. Interplay of small parts results in a material system whose properties in terms of function and design go beyond the individual module. (Gramazio and Kohler, 2010)

5.3 THE TEXTILE MODEL

The ability of a structure to adapt to a load is a highly significant property. The study of this topic involves designs in which material structures may have textile-like generative adaptability. Traditionally, building structures have striven for rigidity whereas textiles embody the properties of elasticity and suppleness. When exposed to an increasing load, the elasticity of wood, for example, may enable deformation instead of destruction. The case study described involves experimentation in which the behavior across different scales is observed. *Integrated tectonic qualities* at different scales can be developed in material construction and

can be demonstrated to contribute to novel topologies and unique tectonic properties. Timberfabric (Weinand, Yves and Hudert, Markus, 2010) is an interdisciplinary approach which integrates architecture, structural engineering and timber construction. This body of experiments is intended to explore and to demonstrate how *textile principles* can be applied at construction scales.

Figure 5. Applying textile principles on construction building scale (Weinand, 2010).

The analogy of micro-scale fiber structures applied to timber-scale building structures can be integrated, since timber has the dual capacities to be formed and to retain a given form (Figure 5). The application of textile principles in the context of timber construction demonstrates an interdisciplinary approach in which architecture turns from traditional design to novel material practice.

5.4 DIGITAL MATERIALITY - THE VARIABLE PROPERTIES MODEL

Fabrication of digital materials (Oxman, N. 2010) with *heterogeneous properties* and controllable form and behavior across a wide array of scales and applications has significant impact on the future of design.

Figure 6. *Beast Chaise Lounge*: Shape and stiffness distribution are informed by structural loading with variable properties directly informed and directly produced within the tectonic model (Oxman Neri, 2010).

In such processes form, structure, and material play equally integrated roles. They promote the application of material as the source of the generation of form. This design principle defines the shift from a geometric-centric design to *material-based design fabrication* in which digital materiality is encoded as a basis for design with fabricated materials (and material forms) of heterogeneous behaviors.

Material-based Design Fabrication is inspired by nature and biological materials (Oxman, N., 2009). In this design approach the shape generation of the material is informed by environmental forces which are acting upon it. In the *Beast Chaise Lounge*, the shape and stiffness distribution are informed by structural loading with variable properties directly informed and directly produced (Figure 5). In the *Carpal Skin*, the local thickness corresponds to strategic areas across the surface area of the wrist in cushioning and protecting it from hard surfaces (Figure 7).

Figure 7. *Carpal Skin*. Local thickness changes correspond to strategic areas across the surface area of the wrist in cushioning and protecting it from hard surfaces (Oxman Neri, 2010)

In nature, such structural bio-materials form micro-structures engineered to adapt external constraints during continuous growth throughout their life span. This is similar to bone structures that are re-modeled under structural or mechanical load. In nature, the sequence *form-structure-material* is inverted bottom-up. For example, in bones and cellular structures the shape is directly informed by the materials from which they are made. In nature, in most cases, material comes first.

Nature's ability to *distribute material properties* by way of locally optimizing regions of varied external requirements, such as bone's ability to remodel its material structure under altering mechanical loads, or wood's capacity to modify its shape by way of containing moisture, is facilitated, fundamentally, by its ability to simultaneously model, simulate, and fabricate material structuring. The digital tectonic here synthesizes principles of natural design which are applied to generate a heterogeneous material structure through digital material in digital fabrication. This design research method has been developed and termed, *Material-based Design Computation* (Oxman, N. 2009). Thus we can now consider the potential of digitally informed materiality and fabrication.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The New Structuralism was found to be a series of theoretical and methodological developments in which *digital tectonics*, *digital materiality* and *digital fabrication* have become a set of key-concepts that are transforming our conventional models of design. Within these explored models of design it is the *structuring, encoding, and fabricating of material systems* that are contributing to a new *material practice* supporting a process of conceptualization by materialization. In this research we have identified new knowledge, related to digital tectonics. The research has focused upon the potential of *informed material and fabrication processes* to return architecture to its tectonic and material sources. It presents a series of informed process models in which form, structure and material

are integrated as an entity in a holistic model of design.

The emergence of *research practice* is establishing a discourse on materialization which contributes to knowledge and experimental designs. This *area* has become an area of design study in which expanded professional knowledge base has become common to both the architect, the structural engineer as well, to the industrial designer and other design fields. How do we educate designers to function as *material practitioners*? Obviously there is a profound influence upon the definition of the requisite knowledge base. Many of the research processes and subjects described above including acquisition of knowledge and skill. Fabrication labs in education which were rare even a few years ago are commonplace today. Thus this cultural shift within design culture is beginning to profoundly transform the cultural institutions of design.

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